

Assessment of Environmental Management Participation in Cultivating a Sustainable Village

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Abstract

This study aims to: (1) determine the level of community participation in maintaining cleanliness in East Mamungaa Village. (2) To know what factors influence the community to participate in maintaining cleanliness in East Mamungaa Village.

The current study used a descriptive research design. This research was located in East Mamungaa Village, specifically in hamlet Five Bulawa District, Bone Bolango Regency. The data has been collected using observation, interview, and documentation. The population was people in Hamlet Five of East Mamungaa Village who participated in the interview on environmental arrangements. Moreover, the sampling of 15 people used a random sampling technique. The type of data used is qualitative including data presented in the form of verbal words which was not in the form of numbers, whose data source is obtained from the East Mamungaa Village Community, hamlet five. The data analysis technique used in this study is a qualitative method.

Based on the results, it was obtained that the people of east Mamungaa Village already have an awareness of how to participate in environmental arrangements, however, some communities still do not understand the importance of environmental arrangements because there are still many communities who are not supportive and prejudiced in new things.

Keywords: Participation, Community, Hygiene

1. Introduction

Recognition by countries around the world that Indonesia is a region that has the most islands, and has a diversity of natural resources throughout the archipelago. To preserve this natural wealth, the government stipulates regulations that become the basis for all Indonesian people to always maintain and preserve it through national policies in all aspects of social life, thus the community must be jointly responsible for managing a balanced living environment, both in the management of provincial spatial plans, district and village governments. In managing a good living environment that involves all parties, it is deemed necessary to have

an understanding between policymakers, policy implementers, and policy users, so that each party understands the importance of protecting, preserving, and utilizing it, and this is a condition that supports the creation good work together.

Spatial management in Indonesia, especially the environment, has an important meaning in achieving sustainable national development goals by making maximum use of it and right on target, with policies that can prevent disputes and abuse of authority.

To preserve this natural wealth, the government stipulates regulations that become the basis for all Indonesian people to always maintain and preserve them through national policies in all aspects of social life, thus the community must be jointly responsible for managing a balanced living environment, both in the management of provincial spatial plans, district and village governments. In the village of East Mamungaa, the management and structuring of residential areas is carried out through community participation, but in recent years the management has not been optimal anymore, even some areas that have been designated as protected areas are used without regard to the safety risks of residents. As a form of cooperation between the East Mamungaa village government and the TNI, they planted 1000 trees near the riverbanks which involved community participation in preserving the environment considering the huge potential of natural resources must be balanced with reliable human resources to create harmony between nature and the environment occupied by residents. This kind of participation has been widely carried out by the East Mamungaa Village Community, Bulawa District, Bone Bolango Regency, developing its territory through village infrastructure development or Environmental Management in previous years so that East Mamungaa Village can win several good awards.

Many studies have been conducted on public participation in development management. To increase the level of public participation in environmental management, efforts need to be made to improve public understanding of the importance of environmental management. In addition, efforts need to be made to allow the public to participate in decision-making in environmental management (Huda & Setyowati, 2020). To increase the level of public participation in environmental management, efforts need to be made to improve public understanding of the importance of environmental management. In addition, efforts need to be made to allow the public to participate in decision-making in environmental management (Irawan & Sukri, 2022). To increase the level of public participation in waste management, efforts need to be made to improve public understanding of the importance of waste management. In addition, efforts need to be made to allow the public to participate in waste processing (Syafi'i & Setyowati, 2023)

The initial observations made, attracted the attention of the compilers to find out more about the role of the village government in carrying out environmental management, especially in the Hamlet V area, Bone Bolango.

Participation

Participation in village development includes community participation in decision-making, and implementation of development, namely the sharing of benefits or profits depending on the results of implementing community activities in the process resulting from these activities. Participating in the development process is seen as a methodology that directs

actors to analyze and find solutions depending on each case being handled, thus forming a framework for monitoring and evaluation (Septyasa, 2013).

Forms of Community Participation

The forms of community participation can also be interpreted as contributions that are given voluntarily (Septyasa, 2013) this can be in the form of:

- a) Participate through the contribution of thoughts.
- b) Participate through the contribution of thoughts.
- c) Participate through social activities, such as providing material self-help, either in the form of money or goods.

Factors affecting the level of community participation

Factors that affect the level of community participation are development plans that are in line with the interests or needs of the community. Therefore, community participation is more achievable if the development plan itself is directed to the benefit of the community (Bintoro, 2017).

Environmental arrangement/management

Environmental management is stated to be an area unit that contains objects, power, conditions, living things that affect the condition of the area (Dewi & Wirajaya, 2013). The arrangement and management of the environment has been regulated and statutory regulations, so that its management is based on the principles that have been regulated, both utilization, control, maintenance (*Law No.32 on Environmental Protection and Management, 2009*)

2. Methods

The method used in this research is descriptive method. This method intends to present the situation according to the facts at the location in detail, and systematically, so that the author can obtain and present a more accurate picture of Community Participation in Environmental Management in Hamlet V, East Mamungaa Village, Bulawa District, Bone Bolango Regency.

3. Results

In the results of the study, the researcher explained the interview process from the people of Hamlet V regarding community participation in environmental management.

Instructive Function

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Sri imon Dalangko
- 2) Felmi Hikolo
- 3) Hamsa Dalangko

The question given by a researcher is how a leader gives orders to the community in giving effect to increasing community participation in Environmental Management in East Mamungaa Village, especially Hamlet V.

Consultative function

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Iskandar h Gunibala
- 2) Fitri ningsi djuma
- 3) Nandaria gunibala

The question given by a researcher is how a leader directs, invites, and is directly involved in community participation activities in environmental management.

Community development

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Yamin Bouti
- 2) Ibrahim Kantu
- 3) Asia Olee

The question given by a researcher is how, you can develop to the community about the arrangement of the environment that you live in to be more beautiful.

Mind Participation

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Narmo soi
- 2) Hasisa tangahu
- 3) Abdulah djuma

The question asked by a researcher is how can you participate in thinking in environmental management.

Energy Participation

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Abdul Hamid Hulalata
- 2) Mohamad Hulalata
- 3) Juanita H kadir

Question Asked by a researcher, how did you or was touched by his heart in helping to organize the environment.

Supporting factors

a. Energy Participation

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Rahman Hulopi
- 2) Salma Hulopi
- 3) Nurmala Hulopi

The researcher asks what questions are you able to participate in the management of the environment in East Mamungaa Village.

b. Skill Participation

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Hasan Towalu
- 2) Haidar Gunibala
- 3) Carles Towalu

The researcher asks the question, what are your skills in participating in environmental management in East Mamungaa Village.

Obstacle factor

a) Kurang Dukungan Masyarakat

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Hamid Dalangko
- 2) Ahmad djuma
- 3) Jainudin baderan

The researcher asks the question, what makes you less supportive in terms of community participation in environmental management.

b) Prejudice Against New Things

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Sopyan Palilati
- 2) Sutarjo Gunibala
- 3) Usman Hulopi

The researcher interviewed what can be prejudiced against new things that are new in community participation in environmental management.

Then on the question above, the researcher directly conducts research that can solve the problem according to the answers from the results of the community interviews themselves.

Instructive Function

The answers from each informant are;

- Sri Imon Dalangko gave the answer he said that the order given by the head of the East Mamungaa Village was very important to be heard and obeyed.

- While the answer from Mrs. Feli Hikolo, the order given by the head of the East Mamungaa Village should be obeyed because a good community should listen to what is ordered by a leader in the village
- While the answer from Mr. Hamsa Dalangko. The order given by the HEAD of the VILLAGE of East Mamungaa has the right to determine how the order should be carried out.

Consultative function

The answers from each informant are;

- Mr. Iskandar H Gunibala gave his answer that the Head of East Mamungaa Village prioritizes consultation with the East Mamungaa Village community before making a decision.
- Mrs. Fitri Ningsi Djuma gave an answer that the Head of the East Mamungaa Village every time he carried out an activity, he participated in helping the activity take place
- Mrs. Nanda Gunibala gave the answer that the Head of East Mamungaa Village directs all village officials to succeed in all activities related to environmental cleanliness in East Mamungaa Village.

Community development

The answers from each informant are;

- Mr. Yamin Bouti gave the answer that in order to develop people to care about the environment, an understanding of environmental issues must be given.
- Mr. Ibrahim Kantu said that community development must be based on strengthening cooperation in environmental management.
- Mrs. Asia Olee gave an answer that the development of the community must prioritize the principle of justice in determining attitudes, in environmental management.

Mind Participation

- Mr. Narmo Soi gave an answer that the arrangement of the environment must be based on the participation of the mind so that the environment is well structured.
- Hasisa Tangahu that in structuring the environment, it is necessary to plan how the environment we live in can feel comfortable.
- Mr. Abdulah Djuma that in the arrangement of the environment must be done voluntarily so that our environment remains clean.

Energy Participation

- Mr. Abdul Hamid Hulalata gave the answer that the participation of energy is very important in structuring the environment.
- Mr. Mohamad Hulalata gave his answer that the participation of personnel can encourage success in environmental management.
- Mrs. Juanita H. Kadir gave the answer that the participation of personnel is not enough if it is not accompanied by providing wages because through wages the environmental arrangement will run as desired.

Supporting factors

a. Energy supporting factor

The answers from each informant are:

- Mr. Rahman Hulopi gave an answer that the supporting factor in the participation of the workforce is very necessary because the participation of the workforce is quickly resolved.
- the answer from Mrs. Salma Hulopi that the supporting factor of labor participation must be based on communication with fellow community members.
- Mrs. Nurmala Hulopi that the supporting factor of the participation of workers must be seen from the level of age and education level as well as the type of work.

b. Skill Factor

The answers from each informant are:

- Mr. Hasan Towalu, regarding the factors supporting skills, he gave an answer that for, in structuring the environment, it must be based on skills in planting.
- Mrs. Haidar Gunibala, regarding the factors that support skills, she gave an answer that skills are really needed when we are going to organize the Environment in Hamlet V.
- Mr. Carkes Towalu regarding the factors supporting skills he gave an answer that skill is the ability to do something well, quickly and precisely.

Inhibiting factor

1. Lack of Support

The answers from each informant are:

- Mr. Hamid Dalangko, he said that the inhibiting factor for the lack of community support was the lack of public trust in the village government.
- While the answer from Mr. Ahmad Djuma about the inhibiting factor of lack of support from the community is when people like things that they feel are not necessary for them.
- While the answer from Mr. Jainudin Baderan regarding the inhibiting factor is the lack of support from the community, namely the lack of public understanding of the programs programmed by the village government.

2. Prejudice against new things

The answers from each informant are:

- Mr. Sopyan Palilati regarding the inhibiting factors in prejudice to new things, he believes that the people's trust in the new policies implemented by the government is still lacking, many people do not believe in the new things implemented by the village government.
- Mr. Sutarjo Gunibala, according to him, many people still lack trust in others.
- Mr. Usaman Hulopi regarding the inhibiting factors in prejudice against new things, he said that it was because people always thought negatively about the things they just heard.

4. Discussion

Instructive Function

In accordance with his duties and responsibilities, the Village Head is obliged to guide by giving orders and instructions, as was the view of previous researchers that the instructions

carried out by the village head emphasized implementation, reports, time and place, completed taking into account the time. efficiency. Another opinion is that the village head shows the consistency of a leader in giving instructions and always applies rules according to standards so that it can be ensured that the work given by employees does not deviate from their duties and functions (Efendi, 2019)

Consultative Function

In the deliberation function, the village head of East Mamungaa provides the opportunity to convey opinions, suggestions and ideas from the community and the village head. This is done to perfect what has been done. Real consultation can be applied by discussing so that the problems they are working on can be resolved immediately (Efendi, 2019). This function can work well if there is mutual openness between employees.

Community development

As part of the development of these efforts, it aims to build community capacity by encouraging, motivating and inspiring, as well as developing their potential.

Mind Participation

This form of participation can be done by contributing ideas or thoughts in the process of implementing, controlling, and coordinating all actions as a form of maintaining rights in social life. As stated by Plumer (*Law No.32 on Environmental Protection and Management*, 2009) regarding the supporting factors for participation, namely:

1. Knowledge and skills
2. Knowledge will affect the entire community environment, allowing people to understand whether they understand the stages and forms of participation that exist.
3. Community work.
4. Usually, people with a certain level of work will be able to spend more or even less time to complete it. Often, the underlying reason for the community is the challenge between commitment to work and willingness to participate.
5. Belief in a particular culture
6. A society with a high degree of heterogeneity, especially in terms of religion and culture, will determine the participation strategy used and the methodology used. Frequently held beliefs can conflict with existing concepts.

Energy Participation

Communities are not only recipients of facilities and benefits but as subjects of sustainable development (Dewi & Wirajaya, 2013). Community participation is the right of the community to participate in decision making, manufacture at all stages of the development process, starting with initial planning, implementation, monitoring and environmental preservation.

Supporting and Inhibiting Factors

From the results of previous interviews, it was found that to implement and realize good environmental management, as proclaimed by the Bone Bolango district government in the vision and mission of 2021-2026, there are factors that influence the process, namely;

1. The East Mamungaa Village Government should encourage the creativity of the village community by providing motivation to the community to be more involved in environmental management by participating, both in mind and energy.
2. The inhibiting factor in implementing environmental management in the village is the lack of community support and prejudice against new things that are considered contrary to the customs and traditions of the local community.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

1. In the implementation of the community settlement environment, the village government plays an important role. For this reason, the village government as a leader in an effort to predict these changes must be able to think or act rationally in making decisions. Above all, decisions will be made without burdening the people.
2. The success achieved by East Mamungaa in harmonizing and dealing with the environment cannot be separated from the role of the village government. The village government in this case is the village apparatus or village head on how to make decisions, especially regarding village issues to speed up the process of structuring a settled community environment so that the people of East Mamungaa village, Bulawa Regency, Bone Bolango Regency can understand and manage the environment together.
3. The importance of community participation in the process of structuring the environment and housing so that the community first gets a strong foundation so that the level of community participation can be maximized. Placing the community as the subject of environmental management means that the community is positioned as one of the important and strategic pillars beside the government. so that the community is not only the implementer of development, but in addition the community plays a role as planners and controllers of various community housing environmental management programs, both government programs and programs made. and developed by the community itself.
4. Based on the findings of researchers who conducted interviews and data collection, the villagers of East Mamungaa know how the community participates in environmental management. However, some people still do not understand the importance of environmental management. This is because there are still many people with little support and prejudice about what is new.

Implication

For local communities, this research can provide information about the importance of community participation in environmental management. This is important because communities are the most affected by environmental change. By participating in environmental management, communities can play an active role in preserving the environment and improving their quality of life. This research can also provide input to governments and relevant parties to increase community participation in environmental management. This can be done in various ways, such as increasing public understanding of the importance of environmental management, providing opportunities for the public to participate in decision-making, and providing the facilities and infrastructure needed to support community participation.

For global communities, this research can provide information about the experiences of local communities in managing the environment. This information can be used as a lesson for global communities in efforts to build sustainable villages

6. References

- Bintoro, T. (2017). *Pengantar Administrasi Pembangunan LP3ES*. Jakarta: PT Pustaka LP3ES Indonesia.
- Dewi, A. S. M., & Wirajaya, A. (2013). Pengaruh Struktur Modal, Profitabilitas, dan Ukuran Perusahaan pada Nilai Perusahaan. *Jurnal Akuntansi Universitas Udayana*, 4(2), 358–372.
- Efendi, S. (2019). *Manajemen Operasional*. Jakarta : LPS- UNAS.
- Huda, A. K., & Setyowati, E. (2020). Partisipasi Masyarakat dalam Pengelolaan Lingkungan Hidup di Desa Mojokrapak, Kecamatan Tembelang, Jombang. *Development, Jurnal: Indonesian Journal of Environment and Sustainable*, 12(2).
- Irawan, R. A., & Sukri. (2022). Partisipasi Masyarakat dalam Pengelolaan Lingkungan di Kawasan Ekowisata Mangrove Desa Teluk Bakau, Kota Bengkulu. *Bisnis, Jurnal: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 13(2).
- Law No.32 on Environmental Protection and Management*. (2009).
- Septyasa, L. N. (2013). Bentuk-bentuk Partisipasi Masyarakat Desa dalam Program Desa Siaga di Desa Bandung Kecamatan Playen Kabupaten Gunung Kidul Provinsi Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta. *Jurnal Kebijakan Dan Manajemen Publik*, 1(1).
- Syafi'i, M. A., & Setyowati, E. (2023). Partisipasi Masyarakat dalam Pengelolaan Sampah di Kelurahan Karang Rejo, Kota Malang. *Lingkungan, Jurnal: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Lingkungan*, 15(2).